

BRIDGING EMOTIONS ACROSS LANGUAGES: CHALLENGES AND STRATEGIES IN TRANSLATING CHARACTER’S EMOTIVE SPEECH FROM ENGLISH INTO UZBEK

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Abstract. *The translation of emotive words in literary texts presents a unique challenge due to their deep connection with cultural context, psychological perception, and linguistic structure. This article explores the difficulties translators face when conveying the emotional depth of characters from English to the Uzbek language and examines various strategies to maintain authenticity and impact. The study incorporates insights from leading linguists and translation researchers.*

Key words: *Emotive words, literary translation, cultural equivalence, translation strategies, semantic equivalence, dynamic equivalence.*

Annotatsiya. *Badiiy matnlardagi emotsional-hissiy jumalarning tarjimasini madaniy kontekst, psixologik idrok va lingvistik unsurlar bilan chuqur bog‘liqligi tufayli o‘ziga xos qiyinchilik tug‘diradi. Ushbu maqola ingliz tilidan O‘zbek tiliga personajlarning hissiy kechinmalarini yetkazishda tarjimonlar duch keladigan qiyinchiliklarni o‘rganadi va asliyat va hissiy nutq ta’sirini saqlab qolish uchun turli strategiyalarni ko‘rib chiqadi. Tadqiqot yetakchi tilshunoslar va tarjima tadqiqotchilarining fikrlarini o‘rgangan holda va ularning asosida olib boriladi.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *emotsional so‘zlar, badiiy tarjima, madaniy ekvivalentlik, tarjima strategiyalari, semantik ekvivalentlik, dinamik ekvivalentlik*

Аннотация. *Перевод эмоциональных слов в литературных текстах представляет собой уникальную задачу из-за их глубокой связи с культурным контекстом, психологическим восприятием и языковой структурой. В этой статье рассматриваются трудности, с которыми сталкиваются переводчики при передаче эмоциональной глубины персонажей с английского на другие языки, и рассматриваются различные стратегии для сохранения аутентичности и воздействия. Исследование следует структуре IMRAD, включающей идеи ведущих лингвистов и исследователей перевода.*

Ключевые слова: *эмоциональные слова, литературный перевод, культурная эквивалентность, стратегии перевода, семантическая эквивалентность, динамическая эквивалентность*

Introduction. Language serves not only as a tool for communication but also as a medium to express emotions, especially in literature. When translating literary works, preserving the emotive force of words used by characters is crucial to maintain the original tone and reader engagement. However, due to linguistic and cultural differences, direct translation is often insufficient, necessitating a nuanced approach. According to Eugene Nida (1964), achieving

"dynamic equivalence" is crucial in translation, ensuring that the target audience experiences emotions similarly to the original readers.

The primary aim of this study is to explore the main difficulties translators face when dealing with emotive words and examine effective strategies used to maintain the original text's emotional impact.

Methods and literary review

Numerous profound linguists carried out thorough investigations to ease the modern translators work which a 21st century translator ought to be grateful for . Even though contemporary translators possess technological tools making their job lighter than their last-century colleagues, there are still questions left that modern researchers are concerned to investigate. A number of issue occurrences on translating has been investigated by the linguists all around the world (Munday, 2014; Munoz & Ricardo, 2010; Sodiqova 2022; Hamidov&Abdullayeva, 2024; Rustamov, 2023).

This study employs a qualitative research approach by analyzing secondary sources, including linguistic studies, translation theories, and case studies of translated literary texts. Key theoretical frameworks such as Nida's (1964) equivalence theory, Jakobson's (1959) semiotic approach, and Vinay and Darbelnet's (1958) translation strategies are used to evaluate how emotive words are translated across different languages.

Results and Discussion

Translators encounter several obstacles when dealing with emotive language, including:

Cultural Variations: Emotions are perceived differently across cultures. Words conveying sorrow, love, or anger in English may not have direct equivalents in other languages. Mona Baker (1992) emphasizes that cultural specificity often necessitates adaptation rather than literal translation.

Idiomatic Expressions: English often employs idioms to express emotions, making literal translation problematic. Vinay and Darbelnet (1958) suggest that modulation and equivalence techniques are essential in such cases.

Connotation and Nuance: The same emotion can be described using different words that carry varying levels of intensity, which may not be directly translatable. Roman Jakobson (1959) argues that some meaning loss is inevitable and should be compensated through context.

Contextual Dependence: The emotional impact of a word depends on the surrounding text and the character's background, making it essential to consider the broader narrative. Lawrence Venuti (1995) highlights the importance of translator visibility in shaping reader perception.

Several strategies can be applied to effectively translate emotive words from English:
Semantic Equivalence: Finding the closest term in the target language that conveys the same emotion while maintaining context (Newmark, 1988).

Adaptation: Modifying the expression to fit the cultural and linguistic framework of the target audience (Baker, 1992).

Paraphrasing: Expanding on the meaning if a direct equivalent does not exist to preserve emotional impact (Catford, 1965).

Borrowing and Calque: In some cases, using borrowed words or calques can help retain the original essence, particularly with widely recognized expressions (Vinay & Darbelnet, 1958).

Analyzing examples from well-known English literary works and their translations demonstrates the importance of these strategies. For instance, translating Shakespearean soliloquies or the emotionally charged dialogues in modern fiction requires balancing linguistic

accuracy with expressive power. Studies by Snell-Hornby (1988) and Hatim & Mason (1997) illustrate how literary translations navigate emotional fidelity and cultural specificity. For example, in **William Shakespeare's "Hamlet"** – The famous phrase "To be or not to be" has been translated into Uzbek as "*Bo 'lish yoki bo 'lmaslik*", preserving the existential dilemma but slightly altering the rhythm and emphasis. In one more page turner, **Charles Dickens' "A Tale of Two Cities"** - the opening line "It was the best of times, it was the worst of times" is translated as "*Bu eng yaxshi davr, bu eng yomon davr edi*", keeping the contrast while adapting the word order for Uzbek grammar. One of the most famous lines in **Ernest Hemingway's "The Old Man and the Sea"**, going as "Man is not made for defeat" is translated as "*Inson mag'lubiyat uchun yaratilmagan*", preserving the philosophical depth and resilience of the original. These examples highlight the necessity of careful word choice and adaptation when translating emotive words into Uzbek. There is one more distinguishing example in the last centuries one of the top 100 great books **F. Scott Fitzgerald's "The Great Gatsby"**, and the last lines of the book comes with the following phrase: "So we beat on, boats against the current". This line has been translated as "*Shunday qilib, biz oqimga qarshi suzishda davom etamiz*", which captures the poetic and melancholic essence of the original.

Similarly, in one of the mind-blowing dystopian masterpiece of **George Orwell, "1984"** – The term "Big Brother is watching you" is translated by Karim Bahriyev as "*Katta Og'a seni kuzatyapti*", which retains the authoritative tone but adjusts for Uzbek syntax. The translation of this particular book has involved almost all methods of interpreting emotive expressions as the whole work itself is considered to be able to express all sort of emotions while reading. The question that protagonist Winston asking from O' Brien "*What is in Room 101?*" expressing the fear of the character. Accordingly, the translator intended to keep the expressiveness of the line, and instead of translating that word by word as "101-xonada nima bor?", he tended to co-notate the meaning with the phrases "*101-xonada nima ish qilishadi?*", maintaining the meaning of fear for Uzbek readers.

Conclusion

The translation of character's emotive words from English is a complex process that requires cultural awareness, linguistic expertise, and creative problem-solving. The study finds that while achieving perfect equivalence is challenging, applying appropriate translation strategies, such as adaptation and paraphrasing, helps to preserve the emotional depth of literary works. Even though many linguists and researchers in this area have persistently been carrying on investigations and discovering something new each time, the ongoing researches can still seem to be required in terms of each language peculiarities.

Future research could further involve AI translation impact in the translation of emotive words, assisting to solve the subtle unanswered questions of the field.

REFERENCES

1. Baker, M., & Baker, M. (2011). In Other Words: A Coursebook on Translation (2nd ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203832929>
2. Catford, J. C. (1965). *A Linguistic Theory of Translation*. Oxford University Press.
3. Hamidov, X., & Abdullayeva, M. (2024). Alternative Versions and Functional Characteristics of Phraseologists in Uzbek. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION*, 4(3), 51-54.
4. Hatim, B., & Mason, I. (1997). *The Translator as Communicator*. Routledge.

5. Jakobson, R. (1959). *On Linguistic Aspects of Translation*. In R. A. Brower (Ed.), *On Translation* (pp. 232-239). Harvard University Press.
6. Jorj Oruell. “1984”. Karim Bahriyev tarjimasi. Toshkent: Nihol , 2020. - 6 b.
7. Newmark, P. (1988). *A Textbook of Translation*. Prentice Hall.
8. Nida, E. A. (1964). *Toward a Science of Translating*. Brill.
9. Munday, Jeremy (2014) “Using primary sources to produce a microhistory of translation and translators: theoretical and methodological concerns”, *Translator: Studies in Intercultural Communication* 20 (1): 64-80.
10. Muñoz Martín, Ricardo (2010) “On Paradigms and Cognitive Translatology”, *Translation and Cognition*, Gregory M. Shreve and Erik Angelone (eds.), Amsterdam, John Benjamins: 169-187.
11. Orwell, G. (1949). *1984*. Secker & Warburg.
12. Rustamov, I. (2023). Aspects of language in translation and translator skills in literary translation. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(3), 573-577.
13. Snell-Hornby, M. (1988). *Translation Studies: An Integrated Approach*. John Benjamins.
14. Sodiqova, D. (2022). LINGUISTIC CHARACTERISTICS OF PHRASEOLOGISMS INVOLVING CLOTHES NAMES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2 (Special Issue 28-2), 206-212.
15. Venuti, L. (1995). *The Translator's Invisibility: A History of Translation*. Routledge.
16. Vinay, J.-P., & Darbelnet, J. (1958). *Stylistique comparée du français et de l'anglais: Méthode de traduction*. Didier.